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Publishing Fine-Grained Standardized Metadata – Lessons Learned from Three Research Data Centers

Knut Wenzig,
Andreas Daniel,
Dominique Hansen,
Tobias Koberg,
Mihaela Tudose

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Knut Wenzig, kwenzig@diw.de, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2259-0203>,
SOEP, DIW Berlin, Germany

Andreas Daniel, daniel@dzhw.eu, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0111-8858>,
DZHW, Hannover, Germany

Dominique Hansen, dhansen@diw.de, SOEP, DIW Berlin, Germany

Tobias Koberg, tobias.koberg@lifbi.de, LIfBi, Bamberg, Germany

Mihaela Tudose, mihaela.tudose@lifbi.de, LIfBi, Bamberg, Germany

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Abstract

FAIRness of research data largely depends on the availability of rich and standardized metadata. While such metadata is commonly available at the study level, fine-grained metadata, especially for tabular scientific data, is often lacking (Wenzig/Han 2024). In a project funded by KonsortSWD-NFDI4Society, three research data centers (SOEP, LIfBi, and DZHW) investigate what is required to convert existing metadata into a standardized format and publish it using a common protocol.

1. Motivation

Fine-grained standardized metadata for tabular research data is rarely accessible. The global registry of research data repositories – re3data.org – lists more than 3,300 repositories that collectively provide over 250,000 metadata resources in DDI-Codebook format. However, only one repository uses the OAI-PMH protocol and only 0.7% of the records contain metadata on the fine-grained variable level (Wenzig and Han 2024).

The problem is not the lack of availability of standards: Metadata standards from the DDI family (DDI-Codebook and DDI-Lifecycle, and DDI-CDI—DDI Alliance 2012, 2020, 2025) document research data at a fine granular level, including information about data sets, variables, and their characteristics. Until 2025, these DDI standards only specified metadata in the form of XML files. (This changed with the model driven approach of DDI-CDI and will continue with the next version of DDI-Lifecycle.)

OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative 2015) provides an established protocol that enables metadata sharing and low-level access. It is built for XML metadata and allows for harvesting metadata from a repository by the URL of the OAI-PMH endpoint.

Why is the publication of fine-grained standardized metadata important? While many research data centers already provide high-quality data and metadata services, there are compelling reasons to consider more standardized approaches:

- In principle, standardization can improve the scalability of business processes and free up resources.
- Standardized metadata can be re-used within the Open Data Format (Han, Hartl, and Wenzig 2024) to reduce the cost of managing data files for different software platforms and to deliver multilingual documentation directly to the user's statistical software.
- AI, especially LLMs, can make use of fine-grained standardized metadata in unknown ways – if those metadata are available.

The publication of fine-grained standardized metadata would also contribute to the creation of FAIR research data and facilitate the FAIR-Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016):

- They increase findability, because they provide more content and deeper insights for each kind of search.
- Since datasets in the social sciences are, in most cases, not freely accessible, it is even more important that relevant metadata on the variables - the core units of analysis - are openly available. Furthermore, if the data is no longer accessible at all, there are good reasons (e.g. more open licenses on metadata facilitate

harvesting and storage by third parties) to expect that metadata are still available and, with them, valuable information, especially on the variable level.

- Providing the metadata at the variable level in a formal language would contribute to the interoperability of the data, by improving its comprehensibility for both humans and machines. Using an established standard, like DDI, for the metadata would further enhance interoperability by ensuring consistency and compatibility across different systems.
- Distributing information in domain-relevant standards will result in a better-informed re-use, as field definitions and general descriptions remain comprehensible over time.

The provision of fine-grained standardized metadata offers many advantages, as it enhances the machine actionability and the overall FAIRness of the data. Therefore, it should be considered best practice. However, as outlined, standardized metadata at the variable level remains scarce. This raises the question of whether factors beyond the availability of standards and accessways pose significant obstacles to data providers in generating such metadata. As we demonstrate, this does not appear to be the case, as the necessary metadata is already available and can be published cost-effectively.

Stata and SPSS are widely used in economics and social sciences. Their file formats already contain metadata on variable level, including variable names, variable labels, and categories/value labels. The main challenge is to map the metadata to an existing standard, integrating the mapping the data processing workflows, and making the metadata accessible. In the following we outline our approach by addressing these challenges based on the metadata of three data centers.

2. Three Starting Points

All three partners already manage metadata on the variable level. These are presented to end-users via different portals: www.paneldata.org, variablesearch.lifbi.de, and metadata.fdz.dzhw.eu. The data base for these portals is as heterogenous as the metadata management philosophies:

- SOEP manages its metadata in CSV tables on a GitLab server with standard office software (Wenzig 2019).
- At LifBi, an MS SQL database is the backbone for the metadata, which are managed using a self-developed metadata editor (Wenzig et al. 2016).
- DZHW uses a NoSQL database (MongoDB) to store metadata in JSON files. Metadata ingestion is facilitated through metadata editor with input masks for

general metadata fields, while variable and question metadata are imported using a dedicated JSON importer.

Prior to this project, the partners used this metadata for documentation on custom-developed web portals, but did not officially publish metadata on variable level in a standardized manner.

During the first project phase, the partners committed to target a payload on each of the relevant conceptual levels because this information is already (somehow) available in the three RDCs:

- On the study level, the information that is already used for registering the datasets' DOIs could be re-used. This means that, as a first approach, the digital object for which the DOI is registered should be the one to publish metadata in DDI-Codebook.
- On the dataset level, the file names (with or without suffix), a label, and a description should be recorded.
- On variable level, the name of the variable, its label and an optional description should be available. Pairs of value and labels build the categories (the term used in DDI-Codebook) or value labels (Stata or SPSS terms). It should also be possible to include question texts and all kinds of key words or overarching concepts.
- Each metadata field containing natural language should be assigned a language code. It should be possible to provide alternative translations for those entries.

3. DDI-Codebook

An XML file in DDI-Codebook standard (DDI Alliance 2012) can have five elements below the root-element <codeBook>: <docDscr>, <stdyDscr>, <fileDscr>, <dataDscr>, and <otherMat>.

- <docDscr> contains bibliographic information describing the XML file itself. This is not addressed in the following as it should only contain information about the metadata itself, i.e. who created it, creation date etc.
- The Study Description in <stdyDscr> consists of information about the data collection, study, or compilation that this DDI-compliant documentation file describes.
- Within <fileDscr>, information about the data file(s) that comprises a collection can be stored.
- The section <dataDscr> contains the descriptions of the variables, the fine-grained metadata that are in the center of this project.

- Finally, the element <otherMat> allows for the inclusion of other materials that are related to the study.

The tree structure (DDI Alliance n.d.) provides a good overview of the DDI-Codebook standard, the field-level documentation (DDI Alliance 2014) serves as the reference book for each element.

The use case we show here is an idealized example derived from the actual holdings of the three RDCs. Figure 1 gives an impression of the material we want to document in a DDI-Codebook XML file: Within a study we have two tables (in Stata format) tab1.dta and tab2.dta that are packed to a ZIP file. Each of the two tables contains two variables.

Figure 1: Use Case with two Stata-Files, each containing two Variables, in one ZIP-File within a Study.

Figure 2: Content of element <stdyDscr>

```
<stdyDscr>
  <citation>
    <titlStmt>
      <titl xml:lang="de">TheStudyTitleGerman</titl>
      <parTitl xml:lang="en">TheStudyTitleEnglish</parTitl>
      <IDNo agency="DOI">studyDOI</IDNo>
    </titlStmt>
  </citation>
</stdyDscr>
```

As the study level is of minor importance for this project, the XML code for the element <stdyDscr> in Figure 2 only shows also the single mandatory field of the DDI-Codebook standard <titl> (which implies <citation>, <titlStmt>, and <stdyDscr> are also present). <parTitl> shall be used to provide a translated title. Element <IDno> contains the registered DOI. So, in our scenario the <stdyDscr> (Figure 1) should contain information

on the DOI level, which means for the three RDCs that metadata used for the DOI registration (like study title, author information or the scope of the study) can be re-used.¹

The attribute `xml:lang` is used to specify the language of the field's content. The ISO 2-letter codes, like "de" for German or "en" for English, should be used.

Figure 3: Content of element `<fileDscr>`

```
<fileDscr ID="Filename">
  <fileTxt>
    <fileName xml:lang="de">FileLabelGerman</fileName>
    <fileName xml:lang="en">FileLabelEnglish</fileName>
    <fileCont xml:lang="de">FileDescriptionGerman</fileCont>
    <fileCont xml:lang="en">FileDescriptionEnglish</fileCont>
  </fileTxt>
</fileDscr>
```

The element `<fileDscr>` (Figure 3) should contain information on file level and can be repeated for collections with multiple files. The attribute `ID` can be used for the filename; in our use case it could be `data.zip`. In the next section of the DDI-Codebook XML file, this `ID` can be used to assign a variable to a file. If a repository provides files in different formats, the element should be repeated to describe the two separate files, it also could make sense to use the file name without extension.

Within the element `<fileTxt>`, the elements `<fileName>` and `<fileCont>` contain a label and a description of for the dataset. Again, the attribute "xml:lang" is used to indicate the language of the descriptive text.

It is not always possible to fully describe the structure of a collection containing multiple files across different folders or bundled in a ZIP file. However, if ZIP files (or similar archives) are used, one option is to name all files explicitly—using the `<fileCont>` element for both the ZIP file and its contents to indicate their relationship, at least in a human-readable way.

¹ The three project partners register DOIs through `da|ra`, which provides metadata via OAI-PMH (<https://www.da-ra.de/oaip/>), including DDI-Lifecycle format based on the mapping by Koch et al. (2017, pp. 91-92). The `da|ra` service will be discontinued by the end of 2025, but as a DataCite agent, its metadata records will remain accessible through DataCite (<https://datacite.org/>).

Figure 4: Content of element <dataDscr>

```
<dataDscr>
  <varGrp type="file" var="var1ID var2ID ..." name="tab1.dta">
    <labl xml:lang="en">tab1.dta-LabelEnglish</labl>
    <labl xml:lang="de"> tab1.dta-LabelGerman</labl>
    <txt xml:lang="en"> tab1.dta-DescriptionEnglish</txt>
    <txt xml:lang="de"> tab1.dta-DescriptionGerman</txt>
  </varGrp>
  <varGrp type="file" var="var3ID var4ID ..." name="tab2.dta">
    ...
  </varGrp>

  <var ID="var1ID" name="tab1varA" files=xs:IDREFS>
    <location fileid="FileName"/>
    ...
  </var>
  ...
  <var ID="var4ID" name="tab2varY">
    <location fileid="FileName"/>
    ...
  </var>
</dataDscr>
```

The specification of DDI-Codebook does not locate the information on variables within the element <fileDscr> but introduces the element <dataDscr> (Figure 4) that holds information on each of the variables. The element <dataDscr> is repeatable and if one would want to use the attribute ID for the file name, one could organize the variables of multiple files.

The element <varGrp> can be used to group the variables in datasets. Therefore, the attribute "type" must be "file", the attribute "name" can be used to provide the name of the dataset and the elements <labl> and <txt> can be used to store a label and a description of the dataset. Multilingual content can be accommodated using the attribute xml:lang.

Each variable has its own element <var> within <dataDscr>. The name of the variable is encoded in the attribute "name". The element <location> with its attribute "fileid" is used to assign a variable to a file/dataset. This "fileid" should relate to the content of attribute "ID" in element <fileDscr>. There can also the attribute files in <var> but it is not clear when this attribute should be used and when the element <location> should be used.

Overall, there appear to be too many ways to organize the variables of multiple data tables in DDI-Codebook: While the element `<varGrp>` may be the preferred way, but one could expect that some people will use some repetition of the element of `<dataDcsr>` to group variables, others use the element `<location>` to link variables to files, and others deploy the attribute "files" in element `<var>`. From the perspective of potential harvesters this variety of options seems not to be optimal.

The element `<var>` also is the container for more information on the variables. (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Content of element `<var>`.

```
<var name="VariableName">
  <location fileid="..."/>
  <labl xml:lang="en">VariableLabelEnglish</labl>
  <labl xml:lang="de">VariableLabelGerman</labl>
  <qstn xml:lang="en">QuestionTextEnglish</qstn>
  <qstn xml:lang="de">QuestionTextGerman</qstn>
  <txt xml:lang="en">VariableDescriptionEnglish</txt>
  <txt xml:lang="de">VariableDescriptionGerman</txt>
  <catgry>
    <catValu>Value</catValu>
    <labl xml:lang="de">ValueLabelGerman</labl>
    <labl xml:lang="en">ValueLabelEnglish</labl>
  </catgry>
  <catgry>...</catgry>
  <concept xml:lang="en">ConceptLabelEnglish</concept>
  <concept xml:lang="de">ConceptLabelGerman</concept>
</var>
```

The element `<labl>` holds the variable label as known from statistical software like Stata or SPSS. If available, the element `<qstn>` can be used to store the precise wording of a question. Any other descriptive texts can go into the element `<txt>`. The element `<catgry>` holds a pair of the elements `<catValu>` and `<labl>`, the latter with optional alternatives in different languages. It must be repeated for each labelled value of the variable. Finally, the repeatable element `<concept>` can contain information like topics, terms from thesauri, or other keyword systems. Again, alternatives can be provided by usage of the attribute `xml:lang`.

The three project partners exported the information from their metadata systems. Alternatively, most of the information could have been derived from the Stata or SPSS dataset files: file names, variable names, variable labels, and value labels. It is easy to extract them and convert this information to a DDI-Codebook file, for example by using

the R package DDIwR (Dusa 2024). The proposed mapping could serve as a guideline for the specific implementation within the data processing workflow.

Here is an overview of the initial results: For the SOEP-data, one big XML file was constructed, which contains information on 550 datasets and 107,210 variables. At LIfBi, six XML files sized 12 to 27 MB with information on 204 datasets and 38,730 variables were created. At DZHW an export feature for 28 studies with 31,448 variables was developed. This feature will be integrated into the DZHW portal metadata.fdz.dzhw.eu. This will allow users to directly download one DDI-Codebook XML file for all datasets and variables of the latest version for every data package listed on the portal; as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Introducing the option for downloading DDI-Codebook metadata from metadata.fdz.dzhw.eu

National Academics Panel Study (Nacaps) 2018

Survey Period: Feb 18, 2019 - Jun 1, 2022

Waves: 4

Survey Data Type: Quantitative Data

Data available in: German, English

DOI: 10.21249/DZHW:nac2018:2.0.0

Published at: Apr 30, 2024

Version: 2.0.0 (current) i

Access Way: SUF: Download i

[Add to shopping cart](#) [Go to shopping cart](#)

[Export variable metadata](#)

Click to download the metadata of all variables as a DDI codebook XML.

In case you have problems with the ordering process, please contact userservice@dzhw.eu.

4. OAI-PMH

Besides evaluating the possibilities of extracting DDI-Codebook metadata from proprietary metadata systems, the other aim of the project was to publish metadata in a standardized way using the OAI-PMH-protocol.

The usage scenario could be as follows: The global registry of research data repositories re3data.org lists all repositories that publish DDI-Codebook metadata via the OAI-PMH

protocol. As part of the listing, the OAI-PMH endpoint of each repository is provided. Any interested user can access the OAI-PMH endpoint and query available metadata formats. If metadata is available in DDI-Codebook format, the user can request all metadata in the specified format. With only minor restrictions this approach is already functional today. Most importantly it can operate completely automatically. Using this approach, it is already possible to get access to more than 250,000 DDI-Codebook XML files and analyze them.

The project partners evaluated four different methods to publish DDI-Codebook metadata via the OAI-PMH protocol:

- The “Simple OAI-PMH 2.0 Data provider” (Meyer 2024) does not require a database, as it reads files from folders in a specified folder structure on the server's file system. It would then nest the XML files content as-is into the OAI-PMH response. While the approach is very intuitive and it was easy to set up the software on a test system, it turned out that the XML files are too large, leading to time-out issues.
- The server software “oai-pmh2” (Meyer 2025) depends on an SQLite database (or other) and it is not clear how to import the metadata in the SQLite database.
- Another option would be the metadata server Kuha2 (FSD 2024). However, as it is unclear if the server could process the large metadata files produced in the previous step and if the quite complex installation would pay out.
- We also evaluated the potential of writing our own server software in Python based on the Flask framework, as described by Hallet (2019). It turns out that although initial results were rapidly available, it was not possible to finalize it within the scope of this project.

Ultimately, it turned out that publishing these metadata using OAI-MPH was too ambitious. Thus, the three project partners choose to take different paths: SOEP will publish the metadata at Zenodo, DZHW persistently integrated a download option in its portal (similar to the option Dataverse repository software offers), and LIfBi decided to publish their scientific use file also in the Open Data Format, which is based on DDI-Codebook.

5. Beyond OAI-PMH

While OAI-PMH relies heavily on XML, it seems that there is a shift away from this file format. From the perspective of software development, JSON (in particular, JSON-LD) would be more efficient and clearer as it uses less markup, can handle more complex data structures (nested data objects), and is natively supported by JavaScript. In 2025, the DDI-

Alliance published the new standard DDI-CDI, where CDI stands for “cross domain integration.” While DDI-CDI metadata can be expressed in XML, other formats are also supported, as DDI-CDI defines only the data model, not the metadata file format. This model driven approach will also be used for DDI-Lifecycle 4, where an RDF representation is also available – and it is often stated that RDF will become more important over time as it is better suited for including linked data. However, XML might offer other benefits, especially for long term archiving.

From an RDC perspective, it would be easy to provide metadata as a download, so we want to explore whether FAIR-signposting works with our metadata.

Within FAIR-signposting (Van de Sompel 2023), a standardized qualified link to the metadata would be published on the landing page of the digital object for which a DOI has been registered. This approach ensures that the metadata would then be easily accessible via HTTP and OAI-PMH would no longer be necessary to harvest the metadata. This seems promising as HTTP is a globally established standard, whereas OAI-PMH is a more specialized protocol for distributing XML metadata primarily used in the archival community. By using HTTP-based metadata discovery, FAIR Signposting aligns with common web technologies, enhancing especially interoperability and accessibility.

Enriching a landing page with machine readable information works well for encoding simple bibliographic details, such as author names. LfBi enriches the HTML code of landing pages with a linked JSON-LD file (shown in Figure 7): with this relatively little amount of information they achieve a score of 83% in the fully automated FAIR data assessment tool F-UJI (Devaraju and Huber 2020).

Figure 7: Part of the landing page for <https://doi.org/10.5157/NEPS:SC1:10.1.0>

```
<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/Dataset">  
<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/AboutPage">  
<link rel="describedby" type="application/ld+json" href="https://www.neps  
data.de/Portals/0/NEPS/Datenzentrum/Forschungsdaten/signposting/DOI_10.5157_N  
EPS_SC1_D_10-1-0.jsonld">
```

However, there is no standardized way to indicate: “DDI-Codebook-compliant metadata is available at this link.” There are two approaches to solve this, especially if one wants to enable machine readability:

Option 1 would be the HTML element `<link>`. It can be `<rel="describedby" type="application/xml" href="https://url.to/codebook.xml">`

The only available option seems to be: "Here is an XML file describing the digital object." This is not ideal, as users should not have to download an XML file only to realize it does not follow the expected standard.

An alternative solution would be to mint a specific "rel" type for Codebook metadata (think of it as a sub property of "describedby"). Since the "rel" attribute accepts either a registered keyword or an arbitrary URI, you can use an IRI for that and still be fully HTML5 compliant. Naturally, other people would have to recognize this URI.

Another long-term solution would be to register a media-type for codebook XML, e.g. application/codebook+xml.

Option 2 would rely on JSON-LD and makes use of the Schema.org property "distribution" (Figure 8).

Figure 8: An approach to link to DDI-Codebook metadata which makes use of the Schema.org property "distribution"

```
<script type="application/ld+json">
{
  "@context": "http://schema.org",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "distribution": {
    "@type": "DataDownload",
    "encodingFormat": "https://ddialliance.org/ddi-codebook_v2.5",
    "contentUrl": "https://url.to/codebook.xml",
    "description": "XML metadata document using the DDI Codebook 2.5
    standard."
  }
}
</script>
```

This stretches the semantics of "distribution", but the Schema.org (2024) specification references, at this point, the W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary (Albertoni et al. 2024), which states in a note "Nevertheless, the question of whether different representations can be understood to be distributions of the same dataset, or distributions of different datasets, is application specific. Judgment about how to describe them is the responsibility of the provider, taking into account their understanding of the expectations of users, and practices in the relevant community." If one looks at Stata, SPSS, or the Open Data Format, metadata can be clearly understood as a part of the data.

The property “isBasedOn” would be another option to specify some kind of relation of the digital object, described by the landing page and the linked metadata, but the fit is also far from being perfect.

Ultimately, the community must decide what is the best option for establishing a machine actionable link from a landing page to more complex metadata and not only single metadata elements.

6. Summary

In this project, three project partners show that it is possible to export fine-grained standardized metadata from quite different data sources. While it turned out that publishing those metadata using OAI-PMH is not as straightforward as expected, FAIR signposting techniques would be a good replacement, but work must be done with respect to standardization of access.

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References

Albertoni, R. et al. (2024) Class Distribution - Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2024/REC-vocab-dcat-3-20240822/#Class:Distribution> (Accessed: 20 February 2025).

DDI Alliance (n.d.) XML Schema Outline – DDI-Codebook Version 2.1 – Tree Structure. Available at: <https://ddialliance.org/hubfs/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.1/DTD/DDI2-1-tree.html> (Accessed: 13 March 2025).

DDI Alliance (2012) DDI-Codebook v2.5. Available at: <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-codebook-v2.5> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

DDI Alliance (2014) DDI-Codebook v2.5 – Linked Field-Level Documentation. Available at: <https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/index.html> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

DDI Alliance (2020) DDI-Lifecycle v3.3. Available at: <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-l-v3.3> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

DDI Alliance (2025) DDI-CDI v1.0. Available at: <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-cdi v1.0> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Devaraju, A. and Huber, R. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400> (Accessed: 24. February 2025).

Dusa, A. (2024) DDIwR: DDI with R (R Package). Available at: <https://cran.r-project.org/package=DDIwR> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

FSD (2024) Kuha2 (Software bundle). Available at: <https://kuha2.readthedocs.io/> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

LifBi (2025) JSON-LD file connected linked from landing page. Available at: https://www.neps-data.de/Portals/0/NEPS/Datenzentrum/Forschungsdaten/SC1/10-1-0/DOI_10.5157_NEPS_SC1_10.1.0.jsonld (Accessed: 20 February 2025).

Open Archives Initiative (2015). The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, Protocol Version 2.0 of 2002-06-14. Available at: <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Hallet, R. (2019). OAI-PMH Service Updates. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5438/ppth-pz62> (Accessed: 18 February 2025)

Han, X., Hartl, T. and Wenzig, K. (2024). 'Introducing Open Data Format: A Platform-Independent, Non-Proprietary, Metadata-Enriched, Multilingual Data Format and its Implementation in R and Stata'. KonsortSWD Working Paper 10/2024. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14215268> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Koch, U, et al. (2017) da|ra Metadaten Schema. Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Social and Economic Data. Version 4.0. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4232/10.mdsdoc.4.0> (Accessed: 24. February 2025)

Meyer, S. (2024) Simple OAI-PMH 2.0 Data Provider v1.8. Available at: <https://github.com/opencultureconsulting/simple-oai-pmh/releases/tag/v1.8> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Meyer, S. (2025) oai-pmh2. Available at: <https://github.com/opencultureconsulting/oai-pmh2> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Schema.org (2024) distribution – A Schema.org property v28.1. Available at: <https://schema.org/distribution> (Accessed: 20 February 2025).

Van de Sompel, H. et al. (2023) FAIR Signposting Profile. Available at: <https://signposting.org/FAIR/> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Wenzig, K. (2019) Longitudinal Metadata at the Socio-Economic Panel. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3554859> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Wenzig, K. and Han, X. (2024) 'State of DDI Cloud', IASSIST Quarterly, 48(4). Available at: <http://doi.org/10.29173/iq1116> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

Wenzig, K., et al. (2016) 'Management of Metadata: An Integrated Approach to Structured Documentation' in: H.-P. Blossfeld et al. (eds.) Methodological Issues of Longitudinal Surveys. Wiesbaden: Springer VS, pp. 627-647. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-11994-2_35

Wilkinson, M. et al. (2016) 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. Scientific Data 3, 160018. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18> (Accessed: 18 February 2025).

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Kontakt

DIW Berlin

Sozio-ökonomisches Panel

Knut Wenzig

<https://www.diw.de/staff/de/kwenzig>

kwenzig@diw.de

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KonsortSWD Working Paper

KonsortSWD baut als Teil der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur Angebote zur Unterstützung von Forschung mit Daten in den Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften aus. Unsere Mission ist es, die Forschungsdaten-Infrastruktur zur Beforschung der Gesellschaft zu stärken, zu erweitern und zu vertiefen. Sie soll nutzungsorientiert ausgestaltet sein und die Bedürfnisse der Forschungscommunities berücksichtigen. Wichtiger Grundstein ist dabei das seit über zwei Jahrzehnten durch den Rat für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsdaten (RatSWD) aufgebaute Netzwerk von Forschungsdatenzentren.

In dieser Reihe erscheinen Beiträge rund um das Forschungsdatenmanagement, die im Kontext von KonsortSWD entstehen. Beiträge, die extern und doppelblind begutachtet wurden sind entsprechend gekennzeichnet.

KonsortSWD wird im Rahmen der NFDI durch die Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) gefördert – Projektnummer: 442494171.

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